

moderately resistant to B1 and ShB, and moderately susceptible to BB.

NC493 (IET8989), released as Amulya, is a selection from the land race Najani. It is photoperiod-sensitive and flowers 26-28 Oct. Panicles are long, compact, and well-exserted, with more than 200 long slender grains (6.4 mm

long, 3.1 L/B ratio); 1,000-grain weight is 24 g. Highest yield was 7.4 t/ha in uniform variety trials at Arundhutinagar, Tripura, in 1985. Amulya is resistant to ShB and moderately resistant to BB and SB.

CN570-652-39-2 (IET10001), released as Dinesh, is from a cross

between Jaladhi 2 and Pankaj. It flowers 30 Oct-3 Nov. It has good kneeing ability. Panicles are 22 cm long with 185 short bold grains (5.9 mm long, 2.0 L/B ratio). It had the highest yield (4.8 t/ha) at Chinsurah in 1987. It is moderately resistant to ShB and B1 and moderately susceptible to BB. ■

Seed technology

Hand-operated vacuum packing system for rice seed storage

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We developed a hand-operated vacuum packing system to facilitate dry seed storage. Reducing the oxygen content in sealed containers prevents seed rehydration and suffocates, adult insects. Components of the vacuum packing system are

- a bicycle tire pump, with pump plunger seal or cup in reverse, to use as the vacuum pump;
- a tire inner tube stem valve, to use as a check valve to prevent backflow of air into the vacuum chamber;
- a large food can, irrigation pipe, or pressure cooker to use as the vacuum chamber;

- a lid for the vacuum chamber, used with a rubber gasket made from a tire inner tube and sheet metal or wood;
- a glass jar with a screw cap and gasket or a lid with a plastic inner liner, to use as the storage container.

Seeds are placed in the glass jar and its lid is twisted on snugly, but not so tight that air cannot escape during evacuation. The jar is placed in the vacuum chamber, the chamber evacuated, and the vacuum released rapidly. The rapid intake of air into the vacuum chamber will slam the jar lid down and seal it. Tightening the screw cap will help secure the seal.

A vacuum system using a 16-cm-diameter × 17-cm-high food can requires 8-15 strokes with the modified (4-cm-diameter × 62-cm-high) bicycle pump to attain a vacuum adequate for sealing. We have easily achieved 50-80 kPa

(15-25 inches mercury) suction. Larger vacuum chambers need more strokes to achieve the desired air evacuation.

Including dehydrating agents, such as silica gel, in the storage jar facilitates moisture control. ■

Vacuum packing system: a) bicycle pump with reversed cup, b) tire stem valve, c) rubber stopper, d) sheet metal or plywood, e) rubber gasket, f) jar, and g) food can.

CROP AND RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Physiology and plant nutrition

Rice mitochondria surface membrane contains concanavalin A receptors

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Cell organoids membranes contain the residues of different sugars. The residues in surface membranes provide informational cooperation with other organoids, transport molecules, etc. The presence of sugar residue in the surface membrane of

1. Rice mitochondria stained with Con A gold conjugate suspension.

2. Rice mitochondria stained with Con A gold conjugate.

rice mitochondria and their nature can be shown with the help of the lectins.

We used the concanavalin A (Con A) gold conjugates. This lectin has sugar specificity: D-mannose > D-glucose > N-acetyl D-glucosamine. Rice mitochondria were isolated, fixed, incubated in 20% Con A gold conjugate solution in

phosphate buffered saline (PBS), and studied under an electron microscope.

The rice mitochondrion surface membrane binds the Con A gold conjugate (i.e., contains Con A receptors, probably D-mannose) (Fig. 1, 2). When stained with Os, the rice mitochondrion surface looks as if it consists of global

grains. This is probably the result of protein structure distribution.

The golden deposits structure looks like a ramified tree. Evidently this is connected with the fact that the lectin carbohydrate receptors are parts of the polymer chains. ■

Fertilizer management—organic sources

Performance of *Sesbania rostrata* in calcareous soils

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We compared the performance of stem- and root-nodulating *S. rostrata*, a newly introduced green manure (GM) crop, and *S. aculeata*, the GM crop commonly grown in Bihar, with different levels of inorganic fertilizer in an irrigated ricefield during 1987-89 wet season (May-Dec).

Soils were silt-loam with pH 8.5, 0.60% organic C, and 272-16-119 kg available NPK/ha.

The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with four replications. GM crops were broadcast the third week of May at 30 kg seed/ha. When needed, 17.6 kg P/ha was basal applied. To ensure germination, one irrigation was applied 5 d before sowing.

The GM crops were incorporated 45 d after sowing; on the same day, 35- to 40-d-old seedlings of 150-d-duration

rice variety Radha were transplanted. K was basal applied at 16.6 kg/ha in all plots. P and N were applied per treatment (see table).

GM plant stands were uniform in all plots. Dry matter production and N yield were estimated at incorporation.

S. rostrata added more dry matter and N than *S. aculeata* in all treatments. P

applied at sowing of GM crops was superior to P applied at puddling.

Highest grain yields (3.1-3.3 ma) were with recommended fertilizers; with *S. rostrata* plus P and 40 kg N/ha in two equal splits; and with *S. aculeata* plus P and 40 kg N/ha in two equal splits. Straw yields with these treatments followed the same trend. Net returns were higher with *S. rostrata* plus P and N. ■

Effect of GM crops on rice yield and net return per rupee of investment on pooled (1987, 1988, and 1989) basis, Bihar, India.

Treatment ^a	Dry matter from GM (t/ha)	N accumulated (kg/ha)	Rice yield (t/ha)		Net return
			Grain	Straw	
<i>Sesbania aculeata</i> + P + 40 kg N/ha in 2 equal splits: MT + PI	4.2	76.2	3.1	5.1	1.10
<i>S. aculeata</i> + no P + 40 kg N/ha in 2 equal splits: MT + PI	4.0	72.4	2.8	4.7	1.08
<i>S. rostrata</i> + P + 40 kg N/ha in 2 equal splits: MT + PI	4.3	81.5	3.3	5.5	1.24
<i>S. rostrata</i> + no P + 40 kg N/ha in 2 equal splits: MT + PI	4.0	75.0	2.9	4.8	1.15
40 kg N/ha in 2 equal splits: MT + PI	-	-	2.4	3.9	0.71
80-40-20 kg NPK/ha	-	-	3.3	5.4	1.20
<i>S. aculeata</i> + recommended 40-20 kg PK/ha	4.0	12.3	2.4	4.0	0.85
<i>S. rostrata</i> + recommended 40-20 kg PK/ha	4.1	16.4	2.5	4.2	0.93
Control (no GM, no NPK)	-	-	1.8	2.8	0.51
LSD (0.05)	-	-	0.3	0.4	0.12

^aMT = maximum tillering, PI = panicle initiation, GM = green manure.

Integrated pest management—diseases

Kresek in mature rice plants

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We found kresek in mature rice plants during 1990 in rainfed lowland fields at the BRRI Regional Station experimental farm and in farmers' fields in Barisal. This is the first report of this disease in Bangladesh.

Infested tiller showing normal older leaves and leaf sheaths.

The first symptom appears in the youngest leaf as dense whitish stripes or lesions at the base of the leaf blade. This whitish lesion moves upward through the midrib, which turns brown. Gradually, the leaf turns yellow and rolls along the midrib. It looks like deadheart caused by stem borer, but the dead leaf cannot be pulled up easily. Older leaves and leaf sheaths remain normal and green (see figure).

When a diseased tiller is split, the entire leaf base enclosed by the older leaf sheath appears soft and rotten and